

GENIBIN – IOT-ENABLED GENIUS WASTE MANAGEMENT FOR SMARTER CITY

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Abstract

Waste is a common environmental issues in many developing countries, there are factors which causing waste becomes hot issue such as growth of population and growth of needs which leads to rapid growth of consumption. Overload of waste happened because the limited capacity of trash bin, late trucking and most of waste are thrown away to landfills so there will be tons of waste on landfills whereas many types waste can be recycled and the other problems in developing countries are the knowledge and awareness of the citizen sometimes makes them mixed. Due to the rapid growth of Internet of Things, there are some challenges and opportunities to make cities and its citizen smarter by creating an entertaining look of trash it will help to build the good human habits to put the trash to its category. This research aim of this paper is to present the design of smarter waste management using IoT devices, WiFi module to send data over the internet, ultrasonic sensors to measure the volume for each category (metal and non-metal), proximity sensor to detect the category of waste and LCD to educate people about the category of waste.

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1. Introduction

Digitized society was coming by rapid changing of technology and by now world is entering the fourth industrial revolution or also known Industry 4.0. According to Indonesia investment, Industry 4.0 is supported by five key technological advances and one of them is Internet of Things. In the Making Indonesia 4.0 roadmap by Minister of Industry and it consists of 10 cross-sectoral national initiative and one of them is build national digital infrastructure.² Internet of Things (IoT) is the internetwork between sensors and physical world, these physical devices are connected to wired or wireless internet connection. The idea of Internet of Things are designed to bridge the gap between digital and physical world to improve the quality and productivity of human's life, society and industries. Population of growth in Indonesia is getting higher by the time. Hence, the need of improving life quality is must. Indonesia also has specific problem on waste and people. The relation between them involving education problem it's proven when people don't get used to put the waste by its category and exactly throw the waste carelessly. As an example, there are so many garbage get caught under the former railway bridge in Dayeuhkolot, Bandung regency makes us can walk there. By these emergency situation we realized, Indonesia need something interesting and educating, so we try to build a unique trash which can tell people what category of the litter that they want to put and if people want to build some unique craft we can put specific category without sorting and wasting time. The purpose of this project is an implementation of a low cost, light, attractive and user friendly segregation system for urban households to streamline the waste management process.

In this paper we introduce GENIBIN, an IoT based Waste management system to achieve effective dynamic waste collection. The system consists of one smart bin with two separated rooms, one is for metal collection and second is non-metal collection. We also use Thingspeak for data analysis to send the information to the municipal office. This paper organized as follows. Section 2 deals with related works on IoT based waste management system. Section 3 explains about the sensors we used in GENIBIN. Section 4 explains about the block diagram of GENIBIN. Section 5 explains about the flow

chart Section 6 gives the result of each sensor output and also results of data analysis using Thingspeak and also presents evaluation performance with the Android App, while section 7 concludes the paper and discusses future work.

2. Related Work

On previous research concerning waste management used the technology of GIS (Geographic Information System) which will show the alternative transportation routes of process/hauling dump. On the research, the ArcGis software used to find alternative routes based on a data base created in ArcMap. From the data in the form of a long path, the function of roads, road width, time, and volume of traffic will be created some ranks of the best route will be through any point of the bin.³ Other research determines the schedule for the transport of waste based on the volume of domestic waste each day. This research use sampling method and a direct survey to get the data and do the calculation dealing with the proportion of the garbage it produces based on the number of units and the number of people. From the distribution point of a trash location, will be made the optimum route based on analysis of several variables such as the length of the street, road width, and the motion direction of the vehicle.

From each research, it needs the data in the form of variables that involve in the determination of the optimum route for the transport of waste. We use the technology of ' ThingSpeak ' to connect each point of distributed trashes with google maps so it will automatically show the most effective routes based on the distance, and the condition of the traffic in real time. When compared with the use of GIS software ArcGis, Thingspeak be considered cheaper and easier because it does not require an expensive cost and to find the most efficient/effective routes we don't have to do data variables input from the road that traversed by garbage/waste transport trucks.

By using ultrasonic sensors which are connected on the micro-controller we can automatically find out the volume of trash at any point through remote monitoring, so that the garbage would be transported any notification appears. In addition we also combine trash sorting technology between metal and non-metal using the proximity sensor at each garbage. Of the technology are expected to educate and create community customary habit to sort out the garbage.

3. The Sensors

The main sensor in GENIBIN are ultrasonic and proximity sensor. They can provide information about metal non-metal waste and waste volume. Each sensor have a sensing distance and secure sensing distance described in table 1.

Table 1. Proximity and ultrasonic sensing distance

Sensor type	Sensing distance (cm)	Secure sensing distance (cm)
Proximity	0-0.4	<0.32
Ultrasonic	2-450	2-802-80

Separation metal and non-metal waste are based on a result of proximity sensor, and the volume level estimation on the GENIBIN are based on the measure of distance between waste and surface of GENIBIN.

3.1. Ultrasonic Sensor

This sensor use ultrasonic wave to detect the distance from which object is separated from it. Basic principle of this sensor is it sends the sound waves and it waits for reflection of sound wave from the object under consideration

Figure 1. Ultrasonic sensor working principle

Figure 2. HC-SR04 Ultrasonic Sensor

It should be noted that not all objects are detected by sensor due its shape wherein some waves get reflected back, size might be very small and the positioning angle also plays a role in detection of object. Some objects such as cloths, carpeting absorb the waves, where there is no way for detection of such objects. These are the factors to be noted.1

3.2. Proximity Sensor

Capacitive proximity sensors are used for non-contact detection of metallic objects & nonmetallic objects (liquid, plastic, wooden materials and so on). Capacitive proximity sensors use the variation of capacitance between the sensor and the object being detected. When the object is at a preset distance from the sensitive side of the sensor, an electronic circuit inside the sensor begins to oscillate. The rise or the fall of such oscillation is identified by a threshold circuit that drives an amplifier for the operation of an external load. In GENIBIN we use the proximity sensor with sensing distance 4mm and secure sensing distance under 3.2mm. A screw placed on the backside of the sensor allows regulation of the operating distance. This sensitivity regulation is useful in applications, such as detection of full containers and non-detection of empty containers.

4. Proposed Design

4.1 System Architecture

Waste management can be broadly categorized as: segregation, collection and transportation. Segregation of the solid waste can be done at the root level where the citizens segregate the waste according to wet, dry and medical waste and dump the garbage to the respective garbage bins placed at their homes. The bins will be fitted with ultrasonic sensors to detect the level of garbage collected. We use indicators like LEDs and LCD will for notifications. The sensors will be interfaced to NodeMCU that will collect the sensor data and send it to ThingSpeak cloud where the data will be collected. Based on the data collected, the maintenance person of that apartment gets a message. The message displays the levels of bins of all houses, so that he can be alerted to collect the garbage.

4.2 Block Diagram

GENIBIN is designed for hamlet level to apartment's use, operator gets alerts to collect the waste regularly so there will be no more over volume on each trash bin. There's a main module inside of bin cap consists of 1 ultrasonic sensor, 1 proximity sensor and the microcontrollers. Proximity sensor detect the category of waste based on its capacitance value and ultrasonic sensor utilize ultrasonic wave to measure the volume for each category then sends the category and volume information to the microcontroller so the LCD will show the category of the detected waste and the volume information send through the internet to thingspeak, data analytics will be accessible to operator, the data is sent to the mobile phone via GENIBIN Android application (associated with thingspeak) and the indication of trash volume will be signed by the different alarm sounds.

Figure 3. Working module block diagram

When GENIBIN is turned on location, volume and category from sensors are loaded then displayed on Thingspeak. The main constant which makes Thingspeak data interpretation keep changing is begin when Proximity Sensor detect the capacitance value of waste either metal or non-metal. When the category is detected, category status is being displayed on LCD to inform the user what category of waste that they want to put and the waste detected category is opening simultaneously. By detected category, GENIBIN check the volume for each category regularly. The data collected is being displayed on GENIBIN App, when Proximity Sensor and Ultrasonic Sensor keep working to detect the category and measure the volume for each category so that the value of volume keep updating and if the value is more or less than maximum value then there is alarm to notify the operator.

Figure 4. GENIBIN Flowchart

Arduino is an open source electronics platform based easy-to-use hardware and software. Arduino consists of both a physical programmable circuit board (microcontroller) and a software (IDE) that runs on computer, used to write and upload code to the board. Easy-to-use concept that Arduino offer to the user makes this board become more popular. It also use a simplified version of C++ to easier the user program the Arduino. Arduino keep updating its capability, we use the third revision of this board. NodeMCU stands for Node MicroController Unit is an open source software and hardware development environment that is built around a very inexpensive SoC (System on Chip) called the ESP8266. NodeMCU was created by Espressif Systems on 13 October 2014 shortly after the ESP8266 came out. Many people call NodeMCU as WiFi module but it is actually a microcontroller module with WiFi capability. It is working with operating system XTOS. It consists of 128Kbytes of memory with storage of 4Mbytes, 17 GPIO, Tensilica L106 32-bit as a processor, powered with 3.3 V and current consumption from 10 uA to 170.

5. Results

We succeed to make NodeMCU keep sending volume data by ultrasonic sensor and by volume of 95% it will notify the operator as a sign to take the trash as soon as possible and the location of the trash bin will updated regularly and also GENIBIN can segregate metal and non-metal garbage with accuracy up to 99.9%. While GENIBIN application is being developed we use Thingspeak Data Monitor and html page to display volume and trash bin location, respectively.

Figure 5. ThingSpeak Data Monitor App

Figure 6. Proximity sensor value

Table 2. Proximity sensor value for trash category detection

No	Object	Proximity Value (%)				
1	Scissor	99.90	87.01	88.18	99.90	99.90
2	Knife	99.90	99.90	99.90	99.90	99.90
3	Fork/Spoon	99.90	94.82	99.9	99.9	99.9

6. Conclusion

With integration of some sensors and other components GENIBIN can work as we imagine but there's a lot of things to do with this product, we still have problem with detecting more complex categories of waste because we realized low efficiency of proximity sensor makes waste detection is very limited. Further we want to continue to promote the idea to government and school but before that we want to make sure that GENIBIN can work properly with our official Android application and also we want to add some features like route recommendation.

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